

—Source 2 Description: Exterior view (video) of the Moanstery of Saint Herakleidios and its surrounding area

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

— Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

—Year range: 1965-1966, 2008-2010

↳ Name of excavation

—Official or descriptive name: Excavations undertaken by the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

—Body of water (as distinct from source)

Notes: The Monastery is on the west bank of river Pediaios

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

— Yes

↳ Type of feature

—Clearing

—Water feature

—Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

— No

Notes: The Monastery of Saint Herakleidios is located near the ancient/late antique city of Tamasos (Nicosia district), and the modern villages of Politiko and Episkopeio.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

— Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

— Yes

Notes: The Monastery of Saint Herakleidios is located near the ancient/late antique city of Tamasos (Nicosia district), and the modern villages of Politiko and Episkopeio.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

— Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

— No

Notes: The Monastery of Saint Herakleidios is located near the ancient/late antique city of Tamasos (Nicosia district), and the modern villages of Politiko and Episkopeio.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

— Yes

↳ A single structure

- No
- ↳ One single feature
 - Purposefully placed plants
- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No
- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No
- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No
- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

 - Worship
 - ↳ Worship:
 - Communal
- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Other [specify]: The first basilica was destroyed during the Arab raids. It is unknown how the second basilica was destroyed.
 - ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - For religious reasons
 - Other [specify]: The first basilica was destroyed during the Arab raids
 - ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Human-caused accident
 - Natural phenomena
 - Other [specify]: We do not know exactly how the second basilica was destroyed
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes

Notes: The place did not exist in antiquity

 - ↳ In modernity
 - Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: The place today is dedicated though to Saint Herakleidios, most probably also the founder of the Monastery

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:
– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: There is no evidence regarding sponsors for the foundation of the Mnanstery. It is most probable that there were sponsors throughout its history and the structures which were constructed on the site. The only evidence of sponsorship dates to 1759 (inscription, south wall) and refers to the decoration of the katholikon with frescoes, painted at the expenses of a certain hieromonk Barnabas

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The Monastery was built most probably at the place where Saint Herakleidios has established his cell or a monastic community

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

Notes: The Mausoleum, the Katholikon and the tomb of Saint Herakleidios are attached/juxtaposed

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The katholikon is considered the centre of the life of the Monastery for the services and the worship of the monastic community are taking place there. However, the tomb of Saint Herakleidios is considered also an important place of pilgrimage and worship for the nuns and the pilgrims/visitors of the Monastery

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Grass
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Stone
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Pigments and binders for the frescoes, stones cut for the mosaics

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

–Yes [specify]: Pigments and binders

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes
- ↳ On the outside:
 - No
- ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Frescoes
- ↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
 - Yes
 - Notes: Icons
- ↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

 - Yes
- ↳ Are there gods depicted:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Jesus Christ

- ↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Virgin Mary and Saints, as well as Jesus Christ
- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - No
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Crosses and geometrical motifs are composing the fragments of the mosaics that have survived from the first and the second basilica
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

 - No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they wall paintings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Type
 - 'True' fresco
 - ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Jesus Christ, the Son of God
 - ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - No

- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Scenes from the Life of Saint Herakleidios, the Communion of the Apostles and the Koimesis of Virgin Mary
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: The frescoes date from different periods (8th, 11th, 17th, 18th centuries)
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - No
 - ↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Abstract mosaics:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Mosaics representing crosses and geometric motifs
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - No
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
 - [e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
 - Yes
 - Notes: Inscriptions in Orthodox places of worship are always informative, providing information as to the scenes and the identity of the person(s) depicted
 - ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: An 18th-century inscription mentioning when the fresco decoration of the monuments started (1759), as well as the person who has paid for them (hieromonk Barnabas)
 - ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: Slabs and other stone parts from the 5th-century basilica were used for building a sort of iconostasis in the Medieval Mausoleum of Saint Herakleidios

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Crosses are to be found on the mosaic floors
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
 - Notes: Jesus Christ, Virgin Mary and Saints
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - Yes
 - Notes: Scenes from the Life of Christ, Virgin Mary and Saint Herakleidios
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Unfortunately only fragments are preserved from the different iconographic cycles of the monument

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: This place is not a burial but the tomb of Saint Herakleidios is included in the group of buildings

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: The tomb of Saint Herakleidios

- ↳ In cemetery:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The persons who have lived at the Monastery (previously monks and after 1962 nuns) are buried in the surroundings
- ↳ Family tomb/crypt:
 - No
- ↳ Domestic context:
 - Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Apart from the tomb of Saint Herakleidios, the persons who have lived at the Monastery (previously monks and after 1962 nuns) are buried in the surroundings. The tomb of the first abbess of the Monastery is located in the central courtyard of the Monastery

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: However, the nuns and the pilgrims are praying and worshipping God, Virgin Mary and Saints at this place

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: However, the nuns and the pilgrims are praying and worshipping God, Virgin Mary and Saints at this place

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: However, the pilgrims are praying and worshipping God, Virgin Mary and Saints at this place

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– No

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes
Notes: Services

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Impossible to know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: There is a Divine liturgy every day. More services are also taking place such as Vigils, Matins etc.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– No
Notes: There are no orthodoxy checks. However, the Orthodox ritual is strictly followed

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– No
Notes: There are no orthodoxy checks. However, the Orthodox ritual is strictly followed

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:
– No

Are material offerings present:
– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:
– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:
– Yes
Notes: Offerings to Orthodox monasteries can vary from very luxury (precious) objects or lands to daily-life objects or food

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:
– Yes
Notes: Offerings to Orthodox monasteries can vary from very luxury (precious) objects or lands to daily-life objects or food

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):
– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Offerings to Orthodox monasteries can vary from very luxury (precious) objects or lands to daily-life objects or food

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: Attendance to worship is mandatory for the nuns but it is not for the visitors and pilgrims

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: The nuns of the Monastery are obliged to attend

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: It is required for preserving the monument to future generations

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The different structures of Saint Herakleidios Moanstery were rebuilt and repaired several time throught the Monastery's long history

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The archaeologists and other experts collaborating with the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus, the Church of Cyprus (Bishopric of Tamasos) and the nuns

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The monument is one of the most significant places for pilgrimages on Cyprus, with a long history starting at least in the 5th century. Experts from all disciplines, as well as church and government instances are collaborating for preserving the Monastery and its surroundings

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

–optional (common)

Notes: Pilgrimage to the Moanstery is optional for every person

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

Notes: This is a functioning female monastery and so the nuns are present there full time

↳ Present part time

– No

Notes: This is a functioning female monastery and so the nuns are present there full time

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Female

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: The abess (higoumeni in Greek) is the head of the Monastery and the community

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The Department of Antiquities of Cyprus and the Bishopric of Tamasos, Church of Cyprus

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: The nuns are receiving pilgrims who are giving donations. They as well produce different specialties such as sweets, cookies, etc. They have also a shop selling religious memorabilia and artefacts.

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Notes: The Monastery in the past was leasing lands, while even the monastic buildings were leased. Since 1962 when the Monastery started functioning again, it is possible that there is no leasing anymore, for the nuns are cultivating the lands around the it.

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Notes: The Monastery in the past was leasing lands, while even the monastic buildings were leased. Since 1962 when the Monastery started functioning again, it is possible that there is no leasing anymore, for the nuns are cultivating the lands around the it.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Monastery of Saint Herakleidios, Papageorgiou, A. "Ανασκαφαί Και Αναστηλώσεις Μονής Αγίου Ηρακλειδίου". In Η Παλαιοχριστιανική Και Βυζαντινή Αρχαιολογία Και Τέχνη Εν Κύπρω Κατά Τα Έτη 1965-1966. Nicosia, 1966.

Reference: Monastery of Saint Herakleidios, Papageorgiou, A. "Μονή Αγίου Ηρακλειδίου, Καθολικόν Μονής Αγίου Ηρακλειδίου". In Η Παλαιοχριστιανική Και Βυζαντινή Αρχαιολογία Και Τέχνη Εν Κύπρω Κατά Τα Έτη 1965-1966. Nicosia, 1966.

Reference: Monastery of Saint Herakleidios, Ιερά Μονή Αγίου Ηρακλειδίου. Ιερά Μονή Αγίου Ηρακλειδίου. Nicosia, 2001.

Reference: Monastery of Saint Herakleidios, Τσικνόπουλλος, Ι. Ο Άγιος Ηρακλείδιος Και Η Ιερά Αυτού Μονή Προσκυνητάριον. Nicosia, 1993.